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Mechanical characterization of Trebisacce stone: preliminary results

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ABSTRACT

Trebisacce stone is a building material employed in the past for the construction of structural elements of the historical centre of Trebisacce and for the realization of ornamental elements of the northern part of Cosenza province.

The outcrops of Trebisacce stone belong to the Albidona Formation and are located in the area of Sibari. Lithotypes which have been investigated, limestones, come from historical outcrops situated in the old town of Trebisacce.

The aim of this study is to characterize Trebisacce stone, a carbonate rock with good mechanical and durability properties, and to compare results obtained performing different techniques of analysis. Tests which have been performed belong to both non-destructive techniques (Schmidt hammer test) and to destructive techniques (uniaxial compressive strength test). Relationship between Schmidt hammer rebound values and uniaxial strength was analyzed using different equations. Results obtained demonstrate that Trebisacce stone has good mechanical properties. Non-destructive tests performed show that the Schmidt hammer device could be a useful tool in estimating rock strength values for engineering applications. Furthermore, the comparison between direct and indirect uniaxial compressive values, demonstrate which of the relationships proposed by many authors, could be better for evaluating the uniaxial compressive strength as a function of unit weight and Schmidt hammer rebound.

KEY WORDS: mechanical characterization, Schmidt hammer test, uniaxial compressive strength test.

INTRODUCTION

Trebisacce stone was employed, in the past, as building stone in the northern part of Calabria. Different kinds of artifacts as ashlar, slabs, column shafts, pilasters, portals, balustrades, stairs, paving stones, etc. were made by this material. It was especially employed for structural purposes to realize regular mamposteries or irregular ones, with bricks interpositions. Their use was facilitated by the good characteristics of the rock, its easy workability and by its durability due to its good mechanical properties.

Papers in the existing literature, regarding Trebisacce building stone, concerned only some issues, such as specific aspects focused on sedimentary petrology (Garavelli et al., 1979), the characterization of clays or building elements such as mortars belonging to archeological sites of Trebisacce

(Levi, 2002).

In such a context, this work can be regarded as innovative since it aims at characterizing Trebisacce stone from a mechanical viewpoint and at highlighting the important use of both non-destructive techniques and the relationships of indirect uniaxial compressive strength, for evaluating mechanical properties of rocks (Vellone & Merguerian, 2007).

GEOLOGICAL SETTING

This stone widely outcrops in Sibari area, between the sedimentary successions of Holocene to Middle-Upper Pleistocene composed by gravel, sand, silt and clay of alluvial, lacustrine, eolian, litoral and marine environments and the Albidona Formation composed by arenitic-pelite, pelitic-arenite, pelitic-marl, marl and arenitic-conglomerate turbiditic successions (Selli, 1962).

Outcrops which have been investigated are located in the area of the old town of Trebisacce. According to the geological map of the Figure 1, in this area different outcrops are present: one of them is a clayey-calcareous complex, formed by grey calcarenites, with interbedded green marl, clay, sandstones, and by calcarenites and dark limestones with a high resistance to erosion; marl-torbiditic sandstone complex with a lower resistance than the first complex and with a permeability from low to medium levels; plastic clays and grey, red and green clays, with calcarenitic intrusions, rarely sandstones. This last complex presents a low resistance and a low permeability.

METHODOLOGY

Mechanical characterization was determined by in situ tests and by laboratory analysis. Tests performed belong to non-destructive and destructive techniques.

The “in situ” mechanical tests included strength measurement of outcrops surfaces (Fig. 2) by means of Schmidt Geohammer (L-type), in order to assess hardness characteristics of rocks according to ASTM D5873 (2001) standards. The rebound test hammer housing was held firmly

Fig. 1 – Geological map of the studied area (red rectangle shows the studied area) (Casmez, 1967).

by hand in a position aligned downward (~45 degrees) so that the impact plunger struck at an angle of 45° to the test surface of the outcrops. Twelve readings were examined for three outcrops. After the plunger impact for each reading, the surface of the rock was examined. Readings were rejected if any individual impact test resulted in cracking or any other visible damage. The correlation between the uniaxial compressive strength and Schmidt hammer rebound values

was determined by the different equations reported in the Table 1, where σ_c is the uniaxial compressive strength in MPa, H_S is the Schmidt hammer rebound and γ is the unit weight in g/m^3 . The correlations between H_S mean value and the unconfined compressive strength (σ_c) determined by different equations reported in the Table 1, were assessed and compared to the mean value obtained through the uniaxial compressive strength test (UCS). The International Society

Fig. 2 – Calcarenites and limestones interbedded with marls and clays outcropping in the studied area.

Fig. 3 – MFL SYSTEM uniaxial compressive strength machine.

for Rock Mechanics (ISRM 1981) suggests the use of the Schmidt hammer test to estimate uniaxial compressive strength using unit weight. The relationships employed in this study (Table 1) are the equations of Singh et al. (1983), Shorey et al. (1984) and of Haramy & De Marco (1985) because they obtained very strong correlation between unconfined compressive strength and Schmidt value for different lithological units and the empirical equation of

hammer test and direct destructive test, it was chosen the equation n. 2 (Singh et al, 1983), due to the lowest standard deviation of 12.6, to evaluate uniaxial compressive strength values obtained by the sclerometric test. Mean values obtained from Schmidt Hammer test and Uniaxial compressive strength are reported in the Table 2 while the average diagram of stress/strain is reported in the Figure 4.

Schmidt hammer rebounds reach mean values of 49, 51 and

n	Soruce	Equation	σ_c (Mpa)	UCS (Mpa)	std. dev.
1	Shorey et al. (1984)	$\sigma_c = 0,4H_s - 3,6$	16,4	82,2	46,6
2	Singh et al. (1983)	$\sigma_c = 2H_s$	100,0	82,2	12,6
3	Haramy & De Marco (1985)	$\sigma_c = 0,994H_s - 0,383$	49,3	82,2	23,3
4	O' Rourke (1989)	$\sigma_c = 702H_s - 11040$ (psi)	165,9	82,2	59,2

Table 1 - Various relationships to estimate the uniaxial compressive strength (σ_c) using Schmidt hammer rebound (H_s) and unit weight (γ) (Vellone & Mercurian, 2007)

O'Rourke (1989), because showed high correlation with a regression coefficient of 0.60 from samples of sandstone, siltstone, limestone and anhydrite (Sharma et al., 2011).

Values of unit weight were determined by samples obtained by the same outcrops investigated by Schmidt Hammer test. The unit weight was determined by measuring dry weight and volume of the specimens. Stone blocks were cut obtaining ten cubic specimens of 5x5x5 cm. Specimens have been dried at 110°C, according to the art.5 of the R.D. n. 2232 (1939), obtaining a mean value of 2,57 g/m³.

The uniaxial compressive strength (UCS) was determined on the same cubic specimens of 5x5x5 cm (UNI-EN 1926, 2000) (Fig. 3). Prior to testing, the specimens were oven-dried at 70°C to a constant weight for 24h. After reaching constant mass, the specimens were loaded to failure. Test was carried out at a constant speed rate of 1mm/min MFL SYSTEM with a maximum load capacity of 3.000 kg.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Attending to the values of standard equations obtained comparing uniaxial compressive strength values by Schmidt

Fig. 4 - Average stress-strain curve reaching a maximum value of uniaxial compressive strength (UCS) of 82,2 MPa.

point	H_s	σ_c (Mpa)	UCS (Mpa)
Outcrop 1	49 ± 5,0	98,0 ± 5,0	76,9 ± 12,0
Outcrop 2	51 ± 6,0	102,0 ± 6,0	80,9 ± 13,0
Outcrop 3	50 ± 3,0	100,0 ± 3,0	88,9 ± 5,0
	50 ± 4,7	100,0 ± 4,7	82,2 ± 10,0

Table 2 - Schmidt hammer rebound values (H_s); uniaxial compressive strength values σ_c (MPa) obtained by Singh et al. (1983) equation; uniaxial compressive strength values UCS (MPa) obtained by destructive test for the different outcrops investigated.

50 respectively for the outcrop 1, 2 and 3, with an average rebound value of 50. The uniaxial compressive strength values (σ_c), determined by Schmidt rebounds, are 98.0, 102.0 and 100.0 MPa, with a mean value of 100 MPa and with a standard deviation of 4.7. Uniaxial compressive strength values (UCS), obtained by direct test, are 76.9, 80.9 and 88.9 MPa, for the three outcrops, with a mean value of 82.2 MPa and with a standard deviation of 10.0 MPa.

Comparing the estimated uniaxial compressive strengths (σ_c), obtained using the different equations reported in Table 1, with the direct test results of uniaxial compressive strengths test (UCS), considerable differences in strength values can be noticed: using the equation n.4 of O'Rourke (1989) and the equation n.1 of Shorey et al. (1984) the values of standard deviation are 59.2 and 46.6, so higher for the equation n.4 than the n.1; the equation n. 3 of Haramy & De Marco (1985) and the equation n. 1 of Shorey et al. (1984) underestimate the value of uniaxial compressive strength. Results suggest to use the relationship of Singh et al. (1983), to estimate the uniaxial compressive strength of rock on the basis of Schmidt hammer rebound.

According to the classification of rocks based on compressive strength values and considering mean values of uniaxial compressive strength obtained through the different techniques employed (≤ 100 MPa), Trebisacce stone can be classified as a "strong" stone (Anon, 1977). The stress-strain

Fig. 5 - Failure modes of Trebisacce stone samples.

curves for the rock samples under uniaxial compression can be divided into two phases, the linear elastic one and the failure phase (Fig. 4). As failure modes of rocks could provide useful information in an engineering environment, the failed specimens have been examined, as shown in the Figure 5.

CONCLUSIONS

Tests which have been carried out in this study show that as Trebisacce stone exhibits good mechanical properties, it can be still used as a building material for both historical buildings and for new constructions.

Tests have shown that the prediction of uniaxial compressive strength on the basis of the different relationship gives very inaccurate estimates of actual compressive strength of rock investigated in this study. As shown in Table 1, applying the empirical relationship developed by O'Rourke (1989), not reasonable correlations of σ_c and UCS have been obtained. The empirical relationships developed by Haramy & De Marco (1985) and by Shorey et al. (1984), significantly underestimate the UCS, so that they cannot be used for a reasonable comparison to data obtained through direct tests. The most reasonable equation that gives a value nearer to the mean value of UCS is the equation of Singh et al. (1983).

These measurements can be carried out on site and do not require elaborate specimen preparation and costly test facilities. So, Schmidt hammer rebound values can give meaningful first estimates of uniaxial compressive strength of rock.

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